
Explanatory World Models via Look Ahead Attention for Credit Assignment

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Abstract

Explanations are considered to be a byproduct of our causal understanding of the world. If we would know the actual causal relations, we could provide adequate explanations. In contrast, this work places explanations at the forefront of learning. We argue that explanations provide a strong signal to learn causal relations. To this end, we propose Explanatory World Models (EWM), a type of world model where explanations drive learning. We provide an implementation of EWM based on an attention mechanism called look ahead attention, trained in an unsupervised fashion. We showcase this approach in the credit assignment problem for reinforcement learning and show that explanations provide a better solution to this problem than current heuristics.

1 INTRODUCTION

“Explanation is to cognition as orgasm is to reproduction”

—Alison Gopnik [1998]

To the AI community, explanations may seem like a convenient accessory lying on top of a magnificent and complex cognitive system that communicates our inner thoughts and representations to the outside world. [Gunning, 2017, Miller, 2018, Molnar, 2019, Lundberg et al., 2020]. In contrast, cognitive and social scientists have considered explanations to be central to human learning; they are not an accessory but a major driver of learning. [Hempel and Oppenheim, 1948, Gopnik, 1998, Keil, 2006, Lombrozo, 2006, Williams and Lombrozo, 2013, Woodward and Ross, 2021]. Explanations are regarded so crucial for learning that prediction and control are thought to depend on our capacity to explain events and build relations between them [Lombrozo, 2011]. More-

Figure 1: Explanatory World Models have two primary sources of information: past events, or evidence (E), and an event to be explained, the phenomenon (p). EWM explain a given phenomenon by selecting S past events as a hypothesis (H) to why that phenomenon happened.

over, explanations are known to drive exploration in humans [Legare, 2014], leading to the scientific method.

But, what is an explanation? Explanations can take many forms and shapes, making them challenging to define [Lombrozo, 2006, Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017]. For example, Miller [2018] refers to explanations as an abductive process that, given an event (phenomenon), can identify the causes (explanans) that brought about the phenomenon. Similarly, Elster [2007] characterizes explanations in the following manner: “To explain a phenomenon (an explanandum) is to cite an earlier phenomenon (the explanans) that caused it”. Accordingly, we propose Explanatory World Models (EWM), Fig. 1, a type of world model that learns the environment’s dynamics by explaining. In the context of reinforcement learning (RL), typical world models learn to predict the future directly from a learned representation of the past i.e. from causes to effects. Instead, our approach is

Figure 3: The agent needs to turn all the lights by pressing a series of buttons. The connection between buttons and lights is specified by a causal graph. a) **Chain**: each button activates a light but the red and yellow buttons are disabled until a light enables them. b) **One-turns-all**: the agent only needs to press the green button and wait until the lights turn on. c) **Independent**: each light is turned on independently.

2.1 ATTENTIONAL EWM

In the following, we introduce an implementation of EWM based on attention [Vaswani et al., 2017], depicted in Fig. 2b. The goal of an EWM is to create a hypothesis to why a phenomenon happened. Similarly to the approach taken by Tang et al. [2020], we propose to rank the evidence based on how well it explains a phenomenon using the scale dot product attention. Then it selects the S most relevant events as a hypothesis, similarly to recent Mixture-of-Experts models [Fedus et al., 2021, Riquelme et al., 2021] or the RIMs framework [Goyal et al., 2020]. The ranking of evidence is done using cross-attention between phenomenon and evidence, where the phenomenon is used to compute queries and evidence is used to compute the keys. Note that the value function is set to the identity. We use the differentiable top- S function to select the most informative events as hypothesis.

It is crucial to notice that we cannot directly optimize this model; left aside that explanations are hard to define, there may be many valid hypotheses, and ground truth for these may be hard to collect. Instead, we propose to use a predictive view of explanations that allows us to build an objective that can be optimized for. We say that a hypothesis explaining a phenomenon is satisfactory if it allows predicting the phenomenon only using the hypothesis. Therefore, we introduce a forward model to predict the phenomenon solely from the hypothesis.

Note that since we use the phenomenon in both, the objective and the input, the model could find trivial solutions. In other words, the model could encode the phenomenon in the hypothesis directly, without using the semantic content of the evidence. Allowing only S number of events in the hypothesis creates a second bottleneck that makes easier to encode the right semantic information than just “leaking” the phenomenon. Since we allow the model to use the future, i.e. the phenomenon, for ranking but not for prediction, we call this approach look ahead attention.

Events: In this work we define an event as the delta between

observations $e = o' - o$. Ideally, we would want events to be as independent and disentangled as possible i.e., if a piece of evidence contains multiple objects, the model will assign all these objects as hypothesis. Learning disentangled representations is an important line of research that we hope to see evolve in the near future but that we circumvent by having an environment where only one event at every time step can happen. As in Ramesh et al. [2021], it would be prohibitive for the EWM to work directly with pixels, thus we first use a Discrete VAE to create a low-dimensional representation of each event before passing it to the EWM. The discrete codes are then transformed into a continuous representation using linear embeddings. Additionally, we add relative positional encodings [Dai et al., 2019] to events.

Controlled events: An important factor when planning, imagining or doing credit assignment; is the ability to know what changes in the environment were caused by the agent. This is particularly important in the task of credit assignment where reward must be given only to actions that made the reward happen. To achieve this, we include the action performed by the agent as an additional piece of evidence. As done in Corcoll and Vicente [2020, 2021], if the model needs to use the action to predict the phenomenon, we say the phenomenon was controlled by the agent. Actions are transformed using a linear embedding layer to match the size of the rest of events. Note that special care needs to be taken when computing the temporal mask since we want to only reveal the last action taken. Similarly, the positional encoding for each action must be the same, regardless of where in the sequence it is.

Training and setup: We implement the Discrete VAE using convolutional layers. The query and key transformations of the look ahead attention module are two-layer MLPs with ReLU activations. Similarly, the forward model is a three-layer feed forward network with ReLU activations. We first train the Discrete VAE in isolation with samples collected by a random policy. Then, the attentional EWM and forward model are trained end-to-end to predict the discrete codes of the phenomenon produced by the frozen Discrete VAE.

Figure 4: Vanilla PPO (green) stops solving the task when the discount factor is lower than 0.8. Using EWM to redistribute reward allows the agent to learn even with low discount factors and low redistribution factor (β).

3 REWARD REDISTRIBUTION

An arguably underexplored area of RL is credit assignment. The predominant approach to this problem is to propagate reward based on a simple heuristic: the closer the action is to the reward, the more important it is for that reward to happen. Unfortunately, this approach only works in environments with dense rewards but fails in sparse reward environments where temporal correlations between events do not work, making the learning highly inefficient.

Instead, explanations create a relational directed graph between events where the immediate neighbors of a phenomenon are events in the hypothesis. We can exploit this graph and redistribute reward to events that made the phenomenon happen. Since our implementation takes the top-S events, we remove neighbors with attention weights lower than a set threshold. In RL we typically reward actions, not events; thus, reward is redistributed only to events controlled by the agent (i.e., events where the action is part of the hypothesis). Moreover, we can iteratively explain events in the hypothesis and redistribute reward accordingly. Note that this approach allows us to redistribute reward over arbitrarily long horizons, the only requirement is that relations between two events fall in the same attention window. In practice, we limit how deep we go into the graph by reducing the reward at each level and stop the redistribution if the reward is below 0.1. Finally, the reward to the action of each controlled event is given by

$$r_i = \beta^i r \quad (1)$$

where β is the redistribution factor between $[0, 1]$ and i indicates the level in the graph. The higher the redistribution factor the deeper in the graph the reward will travel.

4 EXPERIMENTS

Our experiments explore the following questions. 1) can these relations be used to redistribute credit so as to achieve more efficient learning? and, 2) can the Attentional EWM learn the right relations between events under different underlying dynamics?

For all our experiments we use the Lights environment Fig. 2a where an agent needs to turn on the lights by pressing a set of buttons. To evaluate how well EWM deal with delays between events, a light will turn on 7 steps after pressing the corresponding button or the previous light turns on. The connectivity between lights and buttons is determined by a causal graph. In some cases, buttons may be disabled until a light is turned on. The three different causal graphs used in this work are shown in Fig. 3. In these experiments we train a EWM for each variant with samples collected using a random policy.

4.1 CAN EWM PROVIDE A MORE EFFICIENT LEARNING?

Here, we want to analyze if redistributing credit using the EWM provides a more efficient learning than traditional credit assignment. In this experiment, we train a PPO agent with and without redistribution using different discount factors and redistribution factors on the Chain variant Fig. 3a). Fig. 4 shows how different discount and redistribution factors affect the learning. A vanilla PPO agent has a hard time solving the Chain variant when the discount factor γ reaches 0.8. On the other hand, our redistribution method allows the agent to learn even when both, discount and redistribution factors are low.

4.2 DOES EWM REDISTRIBUTE REWARD CORRECTLY?

Here we analyze the relations learned by the EWM and how the reward is propagated in a single episode after training the agent. The following results use a PPO agent with discount factor 0.8 and (if applicable) redistribution factor of 0.8.

4.2.1 Chain variant (Fig. 3a):

Fig 5 presents the results on the chain variant, blue line denotes the learned value function at the end of training and green line is the reward assigned to each time step.

On the left, a PPO agent trained without any reward redistribution and discount factor of 0.8. Vanilla PPO fails to propagate reward to far enough events. Relevant events happening far from the reward get little attention and irrelevant events close to the reward too much. Traditional methods have a hard time propagating reward to the right events.

Figure 5: PPO without (a) and with (b) reward redistribution after training on the chain variant. The EWM model can identify the right relations between events and redistribute the reward to key actions.

In contrast, the plot on the right shows a PPO agent trained with the reward redistribution method proposed in section 3 and discount factor of 0.8. Here the right events (pressing buttons and moving to those buttons) are rewarded.

4.2.2 One-turns-all variant (Fig. 3b):

This variant has long delays between action and reward. Here, the agent only needs to press the green button and wait until every light turns on. Pressing other buttons does not have an effect on the lights nor reward.

As shown in Fig. 6a, the model learns the right relations and reward is not given to pressing other buttons nor to the lights turning on since these are not directly controlled by the agent. The model learns to reward the button that causes the lights to turn and the movement of the agent necessary to get to the button.

4.2.3 Independent variant (Fig. 3c):

Here each light is turned on independently and only once all lights are on the reward is given. The complexity of this environment is to relate multiple events to the reward. In previous variants, the reward was always given when the yellow light turned on. Note that here the event of getting a reward can happen when any of the lights turns on but the reward is caused by all the lights turning on.

The results in Fig. 6b show that the EWM can correctly identify that the yellow, red and green buttons caused the reward to happen. Unfortunately, the red and yellow buttons are not in the direct neighborhood of the reward since the model needs to go deeper in the graph (note that the height of the reward indicates the depth in the graph).

5 RELATED WORK

Credit assignment: multiple methods have been devised to improve the credit assignment problem: RUDDER [Arjona-Medina et al., 2019], TVT [Hung et al., 2019], SECRET [Ferret et al., 2020] and Synthetic Returns [Raposo et al., 2021]. All these methods learn relations between events and reward. A drawback of relying on reward to build a model of the world is that there is no learning until a reward is discovered. This is counterproductive since the dynamics of the world are typically stable and can be learned even without seeing any reward. EWM learns how events relate to each other and uses the learned relations to propagate reward to the causing actions.

Slots: RIMs framework [Goyal et al., 2020] and Slot-Attention [Locatello et al., 2020] learn to route information to slots. By limiting the number of evidence the forward model can use, EWM creates an additional bottleneck.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have argued that explanations are not an accessory to learning but a central component. To this purpose, we have introduced a class of models called Explanatory world Models (EWM) and proposed an implementation based on attention. We showcased EWM in the task of credit assignment where our experiments demonstrated that this approach can greatly reduce the sample inefficiency of traditional approaches.

In future work, we want to expand EWM to environments with more complex dynamics. Another open question is how can events be learned in these complex environments? Additionally, explanations are known to drive our curiosity, would agents rewarded by finding phenomena hard to explain explore better? Finally, can world models for planning or learning in imagination benefit from obeying constraints imposed by a EWM?

Figure 6: a) Reward is not redistributed to non-causal events (red button). Moreover, reward is also not given to uncontrolled events (lights). b) The EWM is able to identify that pressing all the buttons was what caused for receiving a reward.

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